

REACTION BETWEEN FERRIC CHLORIDE AND AMMONIUM THIOCYANATE

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On subjecting ferric chloride and ammonium thiocyanate to electrolysis, cataphoresis in an agar-agar gel and diffusion through filter paper at different temperatures, the red colour is discharged around the cathode in electrolysis. The red boundary moves towards the cathode in cataphoresis. This apparent contradiction is easily understood because the red particles carry positive charges but are at the same time easily reducible. It appears from the diffusion experiments that the red particles may be colloidal in nature.

This work is in continuation of our earlier work on variation of colour in mixtures of ferric chloride and ammonium thiocyanate (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 160). That work was later repeated with potassium thiocyanate, and the results with ammonium thiocyanate were substantially corroborated. The variations in colour can be accounted for on the assumption that a red complex is formed in the first instance which undergoes both reduction and hydrolysis. The nature of the red complex was not investigated.

From a review of the relevant literature it appears that before more quantitative experiments are undertaken, it may be useful to clarify whether the complex is of a colloidal nature. This naturally involves qualitative experiments. We have also felt the need of repeating some older experiments, for example, those on cataphoresis, regarding which the literature appears somewhat contradictory. Thus, Schlessinger and van Valkenburg (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1212) considered the red ion to be $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})_6^{3-}$, but Bent and French (*ibid.*, 1941, 63, 568) considered it to be $\text{Fe}(\text{CNS})^{2+}$.

It appears to be an almost universal opinion that the red substance, produced when ferric chloride reacts with a thiocyanate, is due to complex formation. According to Schwarzenburg (*Analyst*, 1955, 80, 713) thiocyanate complexes should on the whole be mono-nuclear, soluble in water, and the complex ions should be negatively charged. The red substance has a high solubility, but the position regarding the other two properties does not appear to be quite clear. There is difference of opinion whether the red ions are positively or negatively charged, and there is no conclusive work concerning the molecular nature of the substance. A re-investigation of these aspects appears to be justified. In the experiments which follow we have studied electrolysis, cataphoresis, diffusion through a filter paper and reduction of the red substance.

EXPERIMENTAL

Electrolysis.—A mixture of 1% ammonium thiocyanate (20 c.c.), ferric chloride (0.0033*M*, 20 c.c.) and water (60 c.c.) was taken in a U-tube (cross-section 1.5 cm height 10 cm) and subjected to electrolysis (10-12 volts). The red colour was rapidly

discharged in the cathode compartment and after half an hour a sharp boundary, colorless/red, was formed at the bottom, with little tendency to diffuse even during several hours. The discharged liquid showed no test for ferrous ions and only a feeble indication for ferric ions. A black deposit appeared on the cathode which dissolved on treatment with HCl, or by itself if the cathode (platinum) was left in the electrolyte, but only after a long time, and responded to tests for iron. This experiment shows at first sight that the red ion may be negatively charged, thus migrating towards the anode and stripping the cathode solution almost entirely of iron, but the treatment of neutral solution with aluminium-mercury couple brings about a rapid discharge of red colour. An acidified solution is also rendered colorless when zinc is added. The discharge of colour observed may therefore be due to reduction, and the experiment does not appear conclusive.

The electrolysis in a number of acidified solutions was repeated. One of the mixtures was 20 c.c. of 0.0033*M*-FeCl₃, 20 c.c. of 1% ammonium thiocyanate, 55 c.c. of water and 5 c.c. of *N*-HCl, so that the mixture was *N*/20 in respect of HCl. On passing the current, the solution became distinctly hot (room temp. 29°). The rate of discharge of colour around the cathode was now much slower and there was no complete discharge of colour as in the neutral solution even after 2 hours. On stopping the current, the colour around the cathode was rapidly regained although there was a general decrease in the intensity of colour throughout the apparatus. It appeared that diffusion of red particles towards regions of lower concentration could adequately explain the observations. The observations were substantially similar when the electrolysis was made intermittent so as to minimise the heating effect. A sharp boundary was, of course, never observed in electrolysis with acidified solutions.

Calaphoresis.—To determine the charge on the red particles more definitely, we carried out a number of cataphoresis experiments. In one experiment we took a glass tube 10 cm long, bore 4.5 mm and partly filled with a warm 3% solution of agar-agar containing 5% ammonium thiocyanate. When the solution had set to a firm jelly, the top was filled with a dilute solution of ferric chloride (about 0.003*M*) and set in a beaker containing a layer of the same. Platinum electrodes were dipped in the two ferric chloride solutions. On application of a potential difference (2 volts) the sharp red boundary always moved towards the cathode irrespective of the fact whether the cathode was set at the top or bottom. The rate with which the boundary moved was not uniform, about 5 mm during the first ten minutes and about 15 mm during the next 45 minutes. The jelly warmed up due to passage of current, and one should have expected a faster rate as the experiment progressed. The heating was quite intense when the ferric chloride was acidified with HCl (about normal in the mixture) and the experiment could be continued only for a few minutes. Even then there was excessive blurring of the boundary and even a semiquantitative measurement of the rate was difficult.

Diffusion Experiments.—We hope that by observing the diffusion characteristics we would be able to judge how far the red substance may be homogeneous and also to obtain some idea about the average molecular weight. Although we did manage to have

a sharp boundary between ferric chloride and ammonium thiocyanate, it soon became blurred and a measurement of the rate of diffusion was not possible using tubes of 5 mm bore. It did not make much difference whether the ferric chloride was almost neutral or acidified with HCl. We propose to repeat these experiments using a sintered glass funnel as the diffusion cell.

We then tried a simpler technique, namely the chromatographic diffusion of the red substance through filter paper. Strips of filter paper, 0.5 cm broad, were cut, treated with the solutions shown in column 3 of Table I, and dried. One end of the strip was dipped in the experimental solutions (column 2). The rate and nature of diffusion were then visually observed. The experimental solution (2 c.c.) was taken in a test tube which was corked after inserting the paper strip to prevent evaporation. The results are set down in column 4. The first figure in column 2 stands for ferric chloride, the second for ammonium thiocyanate and the third for HCl. In some experiments one or more of these substances have been omitted.

TABLE I

Diffusion through variously treated filter paper.

No. of experiment.	Exptl. soln.	Filter paper treated with.	Observations.
1.	0.0006M-FeCl ₃ 0.118 AmCNS No acid	Nil	No visible movement of a coloured boundary. A weak band observed at top after 3 days.
2.	0.0006M-FeCl ₃ 0.118 AmCNS 0.10 HCl	"	First water, then coloured boundary move up.
3.	0.592 AmCNS	0.003M-FeCl ₃	Deep chocolate band in 3-4 hrs. AmCNS and rest of filter paper not coloured.
4.	0.003 FeCl ₃	0.592M-AmCNS	No band at top. Slight yellow band at bottom.
5.	0.301 FeCl ₃	0.592 "	Immediate chocolate band at bottom moves up rapidly. Rest of paper uniform yellow. FeCl ₃ soln. becomes red.
6. *	0.151 FeCl ₃ 0.50 HCl	0.592 "	As in 5, band broader and movement quicker.
7 a.	0.06 FeCl ₃	0.592 "	Neutral solutions: intensity of colour and movement of the band increase with increasing concentration of FeCl ₃ .
b.	0.120 FeCl ₃	0.592 "	
c.	0.181 FeCl ₃	0.592 "	
d.	0.241 FeCl ₃	0.592 "	
e.	0.181 FeCl ₃ 0.20 HCl	0.592 "	Acid solutions: bands broader and more diffuse and upward movement faster (20-30 minutes for reaching top).
f.	0.181 FeCl ₃ 0.40 HCl	0.592 "	

These experiments were performed at room temperature, 29-31°. The experiments 7a to 7f were repeated at 12-13° (in a refrigerator). The rate of movement of the bands was then much slower than could be expected from the simple diffusion equation,

$$D = \frac{RT}{6N \pi \eta r},$$

and curiously enough very slow when acid was present. In acid solutions the bands were broader and more diffuse. The red band tended to disappear after reaching the top, more readily when acid was present. When ferric chloride alone was present in the solution (filter paper untreated), the entire strip turned yellow at a rate increasing with increasing salt concentration (12-13°). In many of the other experiments also a yellow colour persisted throughout the strip irrespective of temperature and presence of acid initially. Such a colour might be expected if ferric chloride underwent hydrolysis, for example. The yellow colour persisted for at least five days.

DISCUSSION

It is not possible to understand all these observations at the moment, but one point appears to be substantially established. Whatever be the nature of the primary product of reaction between ferric and thiocyanate ions, the actual particles are polydisperse, and hence, perhaps colloidal in nature. The presence of acid appears to increase dispersion in favour of lower particle weights, thereby increasing diffusion. Hence, there is apparently no immediate discharge of colour around the cathode in electrolysis with acidified mixtures, since the colour lost is rapidly regained by diffusion from the rest of the solution. Any diffusing boundary which may be formed, e.g. in cataphoresis through agar-agar jelly, is naturally broad and diffuse when acid is present.

At first sight it appears difficult to understand why diffusion should be so slow through filter paper, when acid is present. However, adsorption of the red particles must take place on the cellulose before diffusion could be possible and the former is rendered unfavourable due to decreased particle weight. Perhaps presence of acid may directly produce an unfavourable electrical condition for diffusion, since the diffusing particles carry electric charges.